

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

HYBRID RICE

Performance of IRRI hybrid rices in Andhra Pradesh

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We evaluated yield potential and heterosis in morphophysiological attributes of 11 IRRI hybrid rice lines in Andhra Pradesh in 1984 dry season. Seeds were sown on 2 Jan and 20-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with three replications. NPK was

applied at 120-13-25 kg NPK/ha.

The hybrids were compared with IR50, IR54, and IR36 and local BPT1235. Yield components, leaf area index, and harvest index were recorded and heterosis in different characters was calculated based on the performance of the best check, IR36 (see table).

Yield potential of hybrids HR6, HR8, and HR10 was significantly higher than that of IR36 and HR1 performed at par. The other hybrids had high spikelet sterility and low panicle number and harvest index. HR4, HR5, and HR9 yielded 0.8-1.4 t/ha, had high negative heterosis in panicle number and spikelet

fertility and 60-81% spikelet fertility. All the hybrids matured 8-12 d earlier than IR36, which matured in 112 d.

HR6, HR8, and HR10 had significant positive heterosis in yield (11% to 23%) because of positive heterosis in panicle number and spikelets per panicle, grain weight, total biomass, and leaf area index. Heterosis was positive but not significant for harvest index. Almost all the hybrids had negative heterosis in spikelet fertility. Spikelet sterility in general was higher (>30%) even in standard checks, because there were many cloudy days during the crop season. *ℒ*

Standard heterosis for yield and yield components of some hybrid rices, Andhra Pradesh, India.^a

Hybrid no. and parentage	Yield (t/ha)	Standard heterosis (%)							
		Yield	Panicles/m ²	Spikelets/panicle	Spikelet fertility %	1000-grain weight	Total dry matter at harvest	Harvest index	Leaf area index
MR365A/IR13420-6-3-3-1	4.7	+ 7 (NS)	- 4 (NS)	+12 (NS)	-25 (S)	+ 3 (NS)	+40 (NS)	+13 (NS)	+47 (S)
MR365A/IR13525-2-2-3-3-2-2	3.8	-14 (S)	- 4 (NS)	+ 9 (NS)	-27 (S)	+ 1 (NS)	+20 (NS)	+ 7 (NS)	+18 (NS)
IR10179-2-3-1A/IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2	2.8	-14 (S)	-10 (NS)	+ 2 (NS)	-32 (S)	-10 (S)	-20 (S)	- 3 (NS)	+ 9 (NS)
MR365A/IR18349-22-1-2-1-1	0.8	-82 (S)	-18 (S)	+51 (S)	-73 (S)	+13 (S)	-26 (S)	+ 3 (NS)	+50 (S)
MR365A/IR21015-180-3-3	1.1	-75 (S)	-13 (S)	- 5 (S)	-44 (S)	+13 (S)	+23 (NS)	+ 3 (NS)	+53 (S)
MR365A/IR50	4.9	+11 (S)	+ 5 (NS)	+18 (NS)	-11 (NS)	+19 (S)	+12 (NS)	+13 (NS)	+53 (S)
IR747 B26-3-A/IR50	3.5	-20 (S)	+ 9 (NS)	-18 (NS)	- 3 (NS)	-21 (S)	+20 (NS)	0 (NS)	- 6 (NS)
V20 A/IR9761-19-1	5.0	+14 (S)	+20 (NS)	+ 9 (NS)	+ 1 (NS)	+25 (S)	+40 (NS)	+13 (NS)	+62 (S)
V20 A/IR13419-113-1	1.4	-68 (S)	-14 (NS)	+49 (NS)	-62 (S)	+ 9 (S)	+49 (S)	+10 (NS)	+53 (S)
97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	5.4	+23 (S)	+33 (NS)	+17 (NS)	- 3 (NS)	+ 9 (S)	+22 (NS)	+13 (NS)	+94 (S)
IR10154-23-3-3A/IR15795-232-33	4.0	- 9 (S)	- 2 (NS)	-12 (NS)	- 4 (NS)	+ 3 (NS)	+ 6 (NS)	- 7 (NS)	+76 (S)
IR36 (check)	4.4								
CD	0.3		49	39	11.1	1.8	0.4	NS	0.5
CV %	4.5		5.2	13.7	9.6	3.8	9.1	11.3	8.7

^a S = significant, NS = nonsignificant.

Natural outcrossing of cytoplasmic male sterile V20A

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Natural outcrossing of male sterile parents is important for hybrid rice production. In 1982 dry season, the cytosterile line V20A was planted with the maintainer line V20B.

Seed set on cytosterile line V20A in relation to direction and distance from the pollen source, Bogor, Indonesia, 1982 dry season.

Direction	Seed set (%) at given distance from pollen source					Mean seed set (%)
	30 cm	50 cm	70 cm	90 cm	110 cm	
Northwest	14	7	5	7	5	8
Southwest	5	7	7	4	5	6
Northeast	8	7	5	3	3	5
Southeast	5	7	4	5	2	5
Mean	8	7	5	5	4	6

To synchronize flowering, V20A was seeded 3 d earlier and 3 d later than

V20B and transplanted at the same time in an isolated plot at 1 seedling/hill. The

maintainer line and pollen source was planted in a 3- × 3-m plot at 20- × 20-cm spacing. The cytotsterile line was planted at 30- × 20-cm spacing in 5 rows on each side of the pollen-source plot. The 1st row of 10 plants was 30 cm from the pollen source; the 2d, 50; the 3d, 70; the 4th, 90; and the 5th, 110.

One primary panicle of each male sterile plant was bagged before flowering. The others remained uncovered for natural outcrossing. The flag leaf was clipped for supplementary pollination.

At maturity, V20A plants were harvested individually and seed set was

counted to determine the extent of outcrossing. The bagged panicles did not set any seed, but seed set on uncovered panicles varied with the direction of planting and distance to the pollen source (see table). Low seed set probably was caused by poor V20A panicle exertion. *ℒ*

Isolation of maintainers and restorers for three different male sterile lines

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Thirty-six early- and medium-duration rice, (33 improved Indian varieties and 3

Restorers and maintainers for V20A, Wu 10A, and Pankhari 203A male sterile lines at CRRI, Cuttack, India.^a

Variety	V20A	Wu 10A	Pankhari 203A
Pallavi	M	PR	WM
Gaur-1	WM	PR	M
IR30	-	M	M
Karuna	PR	WM	PR
IR36	R	M	PR
Karjat 184	R	WM	PR
Vani	R	WM	M
Rasi	WM	PR	-
Bharathi	M	WM	PR
IR50	R	PR	PR
Indira	-	WM	M
Palman 579	-	WM	WM
Kanchan	-	WM	WM
Pusa 33	R	PR	M
Prabhat	-	PR	M
Pushpa	-	M	M
Sita	-	M	-
Aswathi	R	PR	WM
Sona	-	PR	M
Palghat 60	PR	WM	-
Pragati	-	M	-
Prasad	R	M	-
Vaigai	-	WM	-
CR190-103	-	M	M
Rajeswari	M	M	M
Kranti	PR	PR	PR
MW10	M	PR	M
Kumar	PR	WM	M
Ratnagiri	-	PR	M
Gaur-10	PR	-	PR
Krishna	M	PR	-
Archana	M	WM	M
Madhu	M	WM	WM
Jamuna	-	M	WM
Karikalan	WM	-	M
Ratna	PR	-	WM

^aR= restorer (80 to 100% spikelet fertility); PR = partial restorer (20 to 80% spikelet fertility); WM = weak maintainer (5 to 20% spikelet fertility); M = maintainer (0 to 5% spikelet fertility); - = damaged seedlings.

from IRRI) were crossed as male parents with each of 3 cytoplasmic, genetic sterile lines — V20A, Wu 10A, and Pankhari 203A — to identify their maintainers and restorers. The F₁ hybrids were grown in the field and in pots in a greenhouse. The main panicles of each plant were bagged and percent spikelet fertility was estimated.

Varieties were classified as effective restorers (>8% spikelet fertility), weak or partial restorers (20 to 80%), weak maintainers (5 to 20%), and effective maintainers (<5%).

IR36, IR50, Karjat 184, Vani, Pusa 33, Aswathi, and Prasad were effective restorers for V20A and Pallavi, Bharathi, Rajeswari, MW 10, Krishna, Archana, and Madhu were effective maintainers (see table). None of the varieties were effective restorers for Wu

10A, but IR30, IR36, Pushpa, Sita, Pragati, Prasad, CR190-103, Rajeswari, and Jamuna were effective maintainers. Similarly, no effective restorers were identified for Pankhari 203A, but 15 were effective maintainers.

IR30, Pushpa, and CR190-103 were maintainers for both Wu 10A and Pankhari 203A. MW 10 and Archana were both maintainers for V20A and Pankhari 203A. Rajeswari was a maintainer for all the three male sterile lines.

IR36 and Prasad were restorers for V20A and maintainers for Wu 10A. Similarly, Vani and Pusa 33 were restorers for V20A and maintainers for Pankhari 203A. The results indicate that the cytoplasm of the three male sterile lines interact differently in the pollinator varieties used in this study. *ℒ*

Pedigree of AR-11 series, upland rices of northeast India

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Juming is a traditional rice cultivation system used by tribes in the northeastern hills of India. No systematic breeding program had attempted to improve local varieties, although some plains varieties were introduced. Although collection, screening, and selection of upland germplasm at Arundhati Nagar Research Station at Agarthala in Tripura did not produce significant results, several hybridizations were attempted. The AR-11 series was developed and became popular. Now, AR-11 varieties are widely planted.

Narkeljuri is a local tall (120 cm) upland rice of Tripura; susceptible to

lodging, blast (Bl), and *Helminthosporium* diseases; and low tillering (1 to 2). It has light green, narrow, long boot leaves, and genes for cluster grains; is photoperiod sensitive, and moderately tolerant of moisture stress; matures in 110 d (May-Jul); and yields 0.8 t/ha. It was crossed with semidwarf high yielding Bala, a South India variety.

The F₁ had intermediate idiosyncrasy, was almost sterile (5% of the embryos developed), and multiplied by repeated cloning.

Only 20 F₂ plants grew. The F₂ progeny was highly sterile and segregated widely for plant height (90 to 140 cm), leaf length and color (dark to light green), leaf pose (drooping, semierect to erect), pigmentation (absent, light to dark), number of tillers (1 to 10), spikelet characters, and cluster grains (1 to 10/cluster).